
OPEN ENVIRONMENTAL DATA PROJECT

OPPORTUNITY BRIEF

*Look to the Local:
Data and engagement in environmental
and climate planning*

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

To witness transformative work in participatory environmental and climate planning, look to the local. When federal environmental and climate policy stalls, states, counties, cities, tribes, and communities often continue to innovate. Local government is also better situated to work with civil society and communities to test innovations, and they face fewer barriers to trying new models for community-centered collaborative planning.

This opportunity brief focuses on the utility of environmental data and processes and procedures of local community engagement within environmental and climate topics. By leveraging openness to support environmental accountability and collaboration, this brief offers a unique insight into relationships between communities, government, research, tech, and philanthropy. While the issues addressed here are complex, the proposed opportunities seek to streamline and simplify processes.

This brief presents opportunities as entry points for data-informed participatory governance to support better climate and environmental planning. The opportunities presented here speak to specific participants within policy and planning landscapes: local, state, and tribal governments; communities and community-based organizations; civil society and academia; and philanthropy. While they are categorized by specific sectors, many of the opportunities are multi-sector in application.

OPPORTUNITIES

There are clear opportunities for both government and non-government actors.

LOCAL GOVERNMENT (CITIES, COUNTIES, MUNICIPALITIES) CAN:

1. Provide avenues for engagement that respect community time and knowledge.
 2. Streamline methods of collecting and recording information.
 3. Pursue models that engage communities in mapping assets and needs paired with direct action.
-

TRIBAL GOVERNMENT CAN:

1. Develop ways to recognize the place of elders as community sources of historic knowledge.
 2. Align open data practices with the CARE principles for Indigenous Data Governance.
-

STATE GOVERNMENT CAN:

1. Address structural, cultural, and informational barriers to participation.
 2. Convene local, tribal, and regional governments to strategize and implement plans.
 3. Build and resource community and organizational capacity to participate in planning processes.
-

COMMUNITIES & COMMUNITY-BASED ORGANIZATIONS CAN:

1. Support government in training, value assessment, and learning from communities.
-

CIVIL SOCIETY ORGANIZATIONS & ACADEMICS CAN:

1. Identify spaces for data collaboratives in tandem with communities and local government.
-

PHILANTHROPY CAN:

1. Provide unrestricted funding and general operating support.
 2. Support widespread learning and adaptation of resources by amplifying grantees' work through network-building activities.
-

LOOK TO THE LOCAL: INTRODUCTION

To witness transformative work in participatory environmental and climate planning, look to the local. When federal environmental and climate policy stalls, states, counties, cities, tribes, and communities often continue to innovate. A shared vision of a healthier future is more immediate at the local level because the impacts of the climate and environmental crises are felt more acutely when you cannot trust the water from the tap, or when air pollution makes it hard to breathe.

Not surprisingly, local governments and Not surprisingly, local governments and communities are also better situated to work with civil society to test innovations, and they face fewer barriers to trying new models for community-centered collaborative planning. This culminates in a more responsive impact, especially when communities and governments work together to build out these shared visions, expand decision spaces and foster trust.

This brief supports environmental accountability by leveraging openness to underpin collaboration between communities, government, research, tech, and philanthropy. We consider the needs and assets of varied stakeholders and interrogate current paradigms in environmental data use and engagement processes. While the issues addressed here are complex, the proposed opportunities seek to streamline and simplify processes. Our aim is not to speak to every stakeholder in a universal way, but rather to articulate how these opportunities depend on contextual positioning. With this in mind, we offer insights and opportunities that are specific to each group (e.g., local government or philanthropy), while also pointing to how the opportunity could expand to other sectors.

This brief specifically considers the utility of environmental data and information, as well as the efficacy of systems designed to collect, use, and communicate this information and knowledge. It focuses on the many roles environmental data can take within local environmental and climate planning processes, including but not limited to: supporting conversations between communities and governing bodies, tracking accountability metrics, informing funding priorities, facilitating visual understanding, and providing evidence to support community organizing.

Focusing on the processes and procedures of local community engagement with environment and climate, this brief considers the design of these spaces and the values expressed through them. Emphasizing multiple points and types of community participation can help mitigate the risk of governments and planners creating policy that doesn't center impacted communities. Several Brain Trust participants agreed that rules aren't written for communities and so it is necessary to change these rules at a structural level, and to question whether governments have the information to know

METHODOLOGY We base this brief on insights from a [Brain Trust held in March 2022](#), which brought together eleven participants from local governments, community-based organizations, tribal organizations, state government, and research spaces around the United States. We discussed how community-developed solutions can enter policy conversations, and how environmental data can better support participatory processes (and vice versa). The participants are quoted throughout this brief.

A NOTE ON "COMMUNITY" The word "community" as we define it here is fluid and context-dependent. Throughout this brief, this takes on many forms, including but not limited to: incorporated or unincorporated spaces, neighborhoods, towns, cities, and counties, that share common issues and goals, understood geographic boundaries, and governance structures.

where to engage communities. In response, we focus on participation as a pivotal and primary step toward collaborative processes, and interrogates how participation is integrated into government decision-making.

This brief presents opportunities as entry points for data-informed participatory governance to better support climate and environmental planning. The opportunities identified within are designed for people working in policy and planning spaces: local, state, and tribal governments; communities and community-based organizations; civil society and academia; and philanthropy.

ENVIRONMENTAL & CLIMATE PLANNING

Environmental and climate planning encompasses the participatory and decision-making processes involving communities and governments as they respond to the climate crisis and environmental concerns. Environmental planning assesses social and economic development, land use, infrastructure, and governance systems as related to natural resources. Examples include planning processes related to coastal flooding, smart utilities, buildings and energy efficiency, public land use, and environmental health hazards.

Climate planning falls into the broader category of environmental planning, and can take the shape of determining priorities of mitigation and adaptation strategies, examining land use and transportation planning policies, and creating targets related to greenhouse gas emissions reductions. Many cities, counties, tribes, and states have already created Climate Action Plans (examples include Hennepin County, King County, Pittsburgh, the Swinomish Indian Tribal Community, and Louisiana). While comprehensive roadmaps vary, these action plans generally outline the activities and agencies involved in mitigation, adaptation, and resilience. Other planning processes might have a more specific concern, such as hazard inventories, vulnerability analyses, sea level rise response plans, or energy use outlooks.

LOOK TO THE LOCAL: ENGAGEMENT & DATA (NEEDS & ASSETS)

This chart points to the varying needs and assets that the various actors have within local environmental and climate planning spaces. Determining these needs and assets helps to deduce opportunities; where to leverage resources, who can learn from who, and what practices are needed across the board.

	Engagement assets	Engagement needs	Data assets	Data needs
Local government	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Ability to use collaborative values - Ability to convene many stakeholder - Ability to pilot new approaches more easily 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Process design that is expedient enough for action, agile enough to take new information into consideration, and iterative enough to connect process to action - Ability to work across agencies and departments 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - GIS data resources - Hyper-local data - Pilot new data governance approaches more easily 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - "Good enough data" - Data and digital literacy, including data governance, data management - Collaborative data governance - Open data practices and agreements - Recognize gaps between government datasets and community lived experience and qualitative data
Tribal government	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Ability to bring communities together people with shared goals and priorities 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Ability to engage with non-tribal governance and across various departments within tribal government 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Indigenous traditional ecological knowledge (ITEK) - Data information, and knowledge structures consistent with Indigenous community priorities 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Data sovereignty, protection, and other practices in line with CARE Principles - Incorporation of lived experience and qualitative data as evidence - Tribal-led regulation of the collection, storage and use of data - Collaborative data governance tools that protects Tribal data
State government	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Convening capacity and resources for infrastructure - Role of capacity building, including clarifying guidance, providing publicly accessible resources, technical assistance, peer-to-peer learning 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - State Chief Data Officers (CDOs) doing more localized data work - Historically siloed departments coordinating and working with each other 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Ability to compile environmental data for compliance purposes (often to send to federal agencies like EPA) - Ability to provide access to consolidated data that communities and local govts can use 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Open data practices and agreements - Data and digital literacy, including data governance, data management - Collaborative data governance tools, including legal infrastructure

Communities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Ability to engage those that might not be immediately interested - Ability to contextualize engagement based on specific needs 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Iterative, dialogic (but not redundant) engagement processes - Capacity (funding, guidance, resources, technical assistance, peer learning) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Community science efforts, monitoring - Local lived experience and place-based histories 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Metrics that answer community's accountability questions, not pre-set dashboards - Collaborative data governance tools - Open data practices and agreements - Incorporation of lived experience, qualitative data as evidence
Community-based organizations	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Ability to convene local, state government and community - Access to funding streams outside of government - Greater ability to pilot new approaches - Ability to template out capacity building resources like trainings 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Increased capacity to track community needs, understand government limitations and opportunities, and understand policy landscapes 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Community science efforts, monitoring - Local lived experience and place-based histories 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Open data practices and agreements - Incorporation of lived-experiences and other non-quantitative environmental information as evidence
Civil society organization and academics	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Ability to act as intermediaries between sectors - Ability to research both social and technical solutions as complex systems 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Open data practices and agreements 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Ability to pilot new approaches to data collection, governance, and communication 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Open data practices and agreements - Collaborative data governance - Community and partner data, understanding of partner data needs
Philanthropy	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Social capital to bring together funding community on shared issues and to learn from communities - Ability to facilitate learning, share resources - Ability to shift approach, be flexible and responsive - Ability to initiate and consolidate partnerships across sectors 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Engagement design that encourages valued processes, incorporating humility, trust, and flexibility 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Ability to prioritize and fund new models for data sharing, collection, use 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Community and partner data, understanding of partner data needs - Collaborative data governance tools - Data literacy, including data governance, data management - Open data practices and agreements

LOCAL GOVERNMENTS

Local government takes the form of cities, counties, and municipal departments or agencies—a Water and Soil Conservation District, an Office of Community Planning and Development, or a Mayor’s Office of Climate Resiliency, for example—each with different data and engagement needs and assets. Common among them is a need to interrogate predominant community engagement models and data systems to provide responsive policymaking.

For each opportunity, we'll include a reference for the other sectors to which this opportunity could apply:

LOCAL GOVERNMENTS

1. PROVIDE ACCESSIBLE AVENUES FOR ENGAGEMENT THAT RESPECT COMMUNITY TIME AND KNOWLEDGE, AND BE TRANSPARENT ABOUT GOALS AND PROCESSES

THE *INSIGHT*

Brain Trust participants commonly remarked that community engagement spaces hosted by local governments are often too formal or out of touch with the people they are supposed to serve. This gatekeeping, intended or not, effectively admits only those who are digitally literate, feel comfortable in the presence of government officials, have extra time, or understand complicated procedures. Several participants acknowledged that this can make community members feel as if they don't belong, or that these engagement processes do not hold space for authentic dialogue, which restricts capacity for involvement. This idea is further exacerbated by a lack of political will and incentive to incorporate public input outside of the dominant narrative or identities, and the reality that meetings can last for hours.

Nikki Cooley, Co-Manager of the Tribes & Climate Change Program at the [Institute for Tribal Environmental Professionals](#), highlighted the need to start from a place of community:

"There are protocols, but you start out with food, with prayer, no matter what faith you're from. You have kids running around. They can be distracting to some, but that brings a sense of who you are doing it for."

THE *OPPORTUNITY*

Local governments can de-formalize avenues for engagement and respect community time and knowledge by providing translation, accessibility, and childcare services. Meetings should provide multiple opportunities for input (e.g., virtual and in-person, written and spoken). Agencies should actively invite communities into these processes, recognize power imbalances, and work to address what a shared and community-grounded vision for the future looks like. Beyond sharing data openly, governments should also improve accessibility and participation by being transparent about their goals and approaches in holding these meetings. At a minimum, they should share detailed agendas and information about who will be present beforehand. Beyond this, it should be made clear to participants how information collected from these meetings is expected to be used. Meeting organizers might even share how information from past meetings has been used. Finally – within the constraints of privacy – meeting summaries or minutes, as well as planned next steps, should be shared with the public. Additionally, local governments should consider supporting people in exploring and interpreting open government data that might be pertinent to the meeting, for example through facilitated workshops. Data intermediaries and ombudspersons (discussed in more detail under State Governments) can facilitate these.

LOCAL GOVERNMENTS

2. STREAMLINE METHODS OF COLLECTING AND RECORDING INFORMATION

THE **INSIGHT**

Local (and state) governments must grapple with the balance between creating an iterative and dialogic process and respecting community time. Anna LoPresti, the former Sustained Climate Assessment Specialist for the [Consortium for Climate Risk in the Urban Northeast](#), highlighted the tendency for governments to repeatedly ask for community input without reviewing any previous history of engagement. She recommended a deliberate process of conducting a literature review on past community engagement and input to reduce over-asks, and to provide a show of good faith:

“These organizations have already gotten community members together and discussed these priorities. We don’t have to reinvent the wheel for the 100th time [...] people have already written down their priorities, so we can take those seriously and move on from that first conversation, to something more meaningful.”

THE **OPPORTUNITY**

Better, more transparent and dynamic documentation can prevent duplicated and/or wasted resources and time. Streamlining methods of collecting and recording information is one way to simplify the process of both collecting and using community input. This will look different depending on the existing systems of information management, but allowing the catalog to be widely shareable and using metadata for content and function tagging will increase its usability.

LOCAL GOVERNMENTS

3. PURSUE MODELS THAT ENGAGE COMMUNITIES IN MAPPING ASSETS AND NEEDS PAIRED WITH DIRECT ACTION

THE **INSIGHT**

Communities and governments must work together to build consensus about what is known, what is needed, and what is possible. Traditional listening sessions or town hall-style events allow for communities to provide direct input to government, but are often conducted in a bilateral manner (i.e., between individuals and government staff) that does not leave space for collaboration or dialogue between community members. By contrast, mapping sessions allow for multilateral conversations between community members. Jeannette Dubinin, Director of Resilience and Adaptation at the [Center for Planning Excellence](#), commented on the process of creating [LA SAFE Plans](#) in Louisiana:

“The use of the data and combining it with other data into a visual format was extremely helpful in communicating the problem and getting, maybe not necessarily consensus, but at least an acknowledgement of the problem and willingness to do something about it.”

THE **OPPORTUNITY**

Local governments can conduct mapping sessions where local qualitative knowledge can be collaboratively mapped and then directly incorporated into a shared understanding between community and government of 1) environment and climate, 2) assets and 3) needs. These sessions can provide space for communities to work and talk in ways that make sense to them, while simultaneously translating insights into more policy-oriented language and directives. In other words, mapping sessions go beyond creating a space for government to listen: they connect environmental data and community conversations directly to planning work, code and ordinance interrogation, and policy writing. For example, within the LA SAFE co-planning process, [open data from the Louisiana Coastal Protection and Restoration Authority’s 2017 Master Plan](#) (including datasets on land change, flood risk, economic damage, coastal vegetation, and social vulnerability) informed adaptation strategies and laid the groundwork for a “community conversation, honing in on goals and values that LA Safe should pursue going forward.”¹ LA SAFE planners articulated the value in “giving equal respect to different kinds of knowledge, whether the knowledge comes from technical training or formal education, or whether it comes from life experiences, emotional responses or instinct.”² By conducting polls during mapping sessions, they also collected data that revealed residents’ anxiety about flood risk, residents’ perspective on economic opportunity, and other topics.

¹ [More on LA SAFE’s usage of data.](#)

² [More on LA SAFE’s principles and co-design process.](#)

TRIBAL GOVERNMENTS

Tribal governments face unique data and engagement considerations, including an interest in upholding the sovereignty of Indigenous knowledges and data and the ability to incorporate Indigenous traditional ecological knowledge (ITEK) into effective climate and environmental planning. We direct readers to the priorities highlighted by the [Institute for Tribal Environmental Professionals \(ITEP\)](#) at Northern Arizona University (NAU), and the [Exchange Network \(EN\)](#) Tribal Governance Group for strengthening tribal environmental data management, including more support for staffing and IT infrastructure, training and technical support that is relevant and appropriate for tribal staff, and solutions for data management and sharing.

This opportunity differs from the others in this brief in that it is framed with both tribal and non-tribal governments in mind. Non-tribal governments must recognize the significance of integrating ITEK – and the management systems needed to store and use this information – into decision-making spaces and policy.

For each opportunity, we'll include a reference for the other sectors to which this opportunity could apply:

TRIBAL GOVERNMENTS

1. DEVELOP WAYS TO RECOGNIZE THE PLACE OF ELDERS AS COMMUNITY SOURCES OF HISTORIC KNOWLEDGE

THE *INSIGHT*

An insight that was repeatedly brought up by the Brain Trust was the need for recognition of different types of data and a need to re-define “data” itself. Participants pointed to the importance of qualitative data (e.g., stories of lived experiences, photos, personal and community histories), and actively making space to integrate them into policy discussion and decisions. Nikki Cooley added a Tribal understanding to this conversation:

“I can talk to my 90-year-old grandmother. She can tell me about what the land used to look like, what kind of plants have disappeared, where watering holes used to be, etc. She is a long-term monitoring source for me. We need to redefine data, what it means, and what is included. Our elders, [...] our forms of life, they are our libraries of knowledge, and we're losing them very quickly.”

THE *OPPORTUNITY*

Mapping sessions can help fill in knowledge gaps, but local governments should make the most of these by respecting community time, honing in on the most prioritized and actionable plans or policies in question. Such a collective process also presents the opportunity for agencies to work beyond silos, legitimize community environmental data and knowledge, engage people and organizations in community science, and promote research by and for those actively seeking to strengthen their communities. Recognizing the place of elders as community monitors points to inextricable links between social, health, and data systems, as well as the need to integrate social and health needs into data collection and management considerations. Tribes have always been data creators, users, and stewards, and data are embedded in Indigenous instructional practices and cultural principles, such as community roles and responsibilities.³ In application, this recognition of elder knowledge can look different in various contexts. Alongside local governments, for example, this could translate to listening sessions specifically catered to gathering and incorporating oral and written histories into comprehensive or climate planning. There is also an opportunity for philanthropy to deliberately fund community-based organizations that provide services to elders and older community members, recognizing them as knowledge-holders and essential assets in policy and planning decision making.

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The National Congress of American Indians Resolution #KAN-18-011: [Support of US Indigenous Data Sovereignty and Inclusion of Tribes in the Development of Tribal Data Governance Principles.](#)

TRIBAL GOVERNMENTS

2. ALIGN OPEN DATA PRACTICES WITH THE CARE PRINCIPLES FOR INDIGENOUS DATA GOVERNANCE

THE *INSIGHT*

Government agencies at all levels have increasingly adopted the [FAIR Data Principles](#) since their introduction in 2016, prioritizing the Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability, and Reuse of datasets. This adoption has accelerated in recent years as the global Covid-19 pandemic has laid bare the risks of not sharing usable data in times of emergency. While FAIR provides clear criteria for sharing open data, it does not address several ethical concerns unique to Indigenous data such as ownership, community engagement, and harm mitigation.

THE *OPPORTUNITY*

As governments continue to adopt FAIR data principles, it will be important to align open practices with the CARE Principles for Indigenous Data Governance as articulated by the Global Indigenous Data Alliance: Collective Benefit, Authority to Control, Responsibility, and Ethics. And in many cases, governments seeking to share data more transparently may need to prioritize CARE over FAIR, or take extra steps to define “cultural metadata”, track provenance, or otherwise collect and govern data in a way that is consistent with local Indigenous values. While the CARE principles were written to center the interests of Indigenous Peoples, they may also apply to other environmentally-vulnerable communities who are a part of local planning processes.

INSIGHTS & OPPORTUNITIES

STATE GOVERNMENTS

States are critical players in environmental and climate planning: they wield considerable regulatory power that affects county and city governments, communities, and businesses. They also hold and distribute resources to these entities to support their work. The size and complexity of organizational structures and regulations, however, can present challenges. A community or organization might not be aware of a funding opportunity, for example; or, when they are aware, they may lack the capacity or resources to provide state programs with relevant information or make compelling proposals based on funding guidelines. Local government, on the other hand, may find it easier to navigate and engage state government, but they may be siloed, unaware of how other cities, counties, and municipalities are approaching planning processes or using environmental data.

For each opportunity, we'll include a reference for the other sectors to which this opportunity could apply:

STATE GOVERNMENTS

1. ADDRESS STRUCTURAL, CULTURAL, AND INFORMATION BARRIERS TO ACCESS AND PARTICIPATION.

THE **INSIGHT**

State agencies often store and compile large volumes of environmental data collected for compliance purposes or for otherwise informing environmental planning. While such data might be helpful to communities, organizations, and research institutions seeking to understand impacts on local health and ecosystems, these data are not always shared in ways that align with FAIR principles. Even when data seekers are aware a dataset exists, they may not know how to access or use it. And policies designed to shield privacy or proprietary information may prevent access to data in anything but aggregate form or at scales too large to be useful to local communities. For instance, utility data may be publicly accessible at the city- or county-level but not at the

THE **OPPORTUNITY**

As a starting point, state governments should adopt Master Data Sharing Agreements, collaboratively designed with communities and other stakeholder groups, to set data management standards and establish processes for safely sharing fine-grained and de-identified datasets with the public. Relatedly, statewide data policies can drive a culture of sharing by creating a presumption of openness among agencies, and by providing guidance for agencies to share data openly in usable formats, as well as to publish data dictionaries and useful metadata. States (as well as cities, counties, and universities) can also look to models such as the [Western Pennsylvania Data Center's](#), which leverages both digital and legal infrastructure to support community engagement with government data.

States should also hire Chief Data Officers (CDOs) and agency data officers with backgrounds and expertise in library science and curation, rather than solely data analysis or IT – a recommendation put forth by Katya Abazaijan, Fellow at the [Beeck Center for Social Impact and Innovation](#). Such officers would ensure that data practices meet standards set in Master Sharing Agreements and data policies, and establish collaborative data governance practices. They could also offer guidance and technical assistance to agency staff regarding data quality, curation, and sharing. Oregon's CDO, for example, established an advisory group in 2020 to develop a [state data strategy](#) that prioritizes openness, ethics, and accountability. But as Katya Abazaijan discussed:⁴

"[many] governments aren't doing the cultural work to create a welcoming place for people with these ideas. It's really hard to work in government if you are trying to do things that are more transparent and community-minded."

For states that have not yet established CDO positions, or want to expand their capacity to take on this kind of work, programs like Georgetown's [Data Labs](#) offer long-term training on open and responsible data governance. In addition, states can employ data intermediaries or ombudspople who can liaise between communities and state agencies, help users find and access data, and advocate for system improvements.

⁴ See Results for America's 2020 [State Standard of Excellence](#) for examples of state efforts to implement data sharing agreements and data policies.

STATE GOVERNMENTS

2. CONVENE COMMUNITIES AND STATE AGENCIES TO SHARE INFORMATION AND ENABLE LOCAL INPUT ON STATEWIDE POLICY AND ACTION.

THE **INSIGHT**

Local, tribal, and regional governing bodies vary in their jurisdictions and authority to enact or enforce environmental policy. Further, by developing environmental or climate resilience plans in isolation from each other or from state government, they risk creating plans that are based on an incomplete picture and are therefore not actionable. On the other side, state agencies that support climate planning and enforce state-wide environmental policy lack avenues for obtaining local input.

THE **OPPORTUNITY**

States can take on the role of convening local actors and relevant agencies to co-develop plans, build consensus, and incorporate local perspectives on approaches to governance. The state of Washington's 2021 Healthy Environment for All ([HEAL](#)) Act, for example, guides environmental planning among seven state agencies with varying authority. It also established an Environmental Justice Council representing diverse community perspectives to advise the covered agencies on implementation and tracking, as well as state legislature on environmental policy and action. Importantly, these agencies must provide annual updates regarding their plans to this council.

Granular environmental data collected by agencies, local governments, and communities will be critical for informing equitable plans. Sharing this data openly can facilitate consensus building among stakeholders with diverse interests by supporting a common understanding of root problems. Tools like [Washington's Environmental Health Disparities map](#) are good starting places for identifying overburdened or particularly vulnerable communities.

Community-driven planning and policy processes can also benefit from partnership with states to ensure that they are responding to and leveraging actionable policy, i.e., with real enforcement capacity and in relation to the appropriate jurisdictions. And, as one Brain Trust participant articulated, when states convene more local levels of government, they can develop:

"[a bottom-up] policy that the community has investment in and that speaks to their identity and belonging."

STATE GOVERNMENTS

3. BUILD COMMUNITY AND ORGANIZATIONAL CAPACITY TO PARTICIPATE IN PLANNING PROCESSES

THE *INSIGHT*

States often offer funding and other support for communities to design or implement environmental or climate plans, but many communities and community organizations may be unaware of these opportunities or lack the resources—informational, human, social, etc.—to access such support. The complexities of navigating agency processes, strategizing, and preparing proposals present barriers to access for less resourced organizations and communities—often those most impacted by climate change and pollution.

THE **OPPORTUNITY**

State agencies can reduce these barriers by funneling resources to capacity building programs, a point underscored by Emi Wang of the [Greenlining Institute](#). For example, California State Bill 1072, which established Regional Climate Collaboratives, was a result of years of advocacy from and partnership with community organizations like the Greenlining Institute. These collaboratives serve as local hubs where communities can come together, strategize, develop partnerships, and apply for state funding. While SB-1072 doesn't explicitly direct funding, it did lead to the creation of the Partners Advancing Climate Equity (PACE) program to provide training, mentorship, and technical assistance to frontline community leaders. PACE is managed by the Strategic Growth Council (SGC), a state organization that also leads an inter-agency working group to develop technical assistance guidelines. Depending on communities' existing capacity and access to resources, these programs may need to focus on building a range of skills, from digital literacy to proposal writing and budgeting.

Where they exist and are useful, open data portals can be leveraged as sources of baseline information and evidence (or lack thereof) to be cited in proposals. As mentioned previously, data ombudspersons and intermediaries can support these capacity building programs by helping organizations find and use data to support their ideas. There is a clear need for ombudspersons to be independent, credible, and impartial figures. This role has [historically materialized in the EPA](#), and while the contexts differ, the need remains for a role in state government to support communities facing environmental and climate issues.

INSIGHTS & OPPORTUNITIES

COMMUNITIES &
COMMUNITY-BASED
ORGANIZATIONS

A simple, but essential truth drives the recommendations in this section: communities have a vested interest in their rights to exist and thrive. Different communities and community-based organizations have different needs and assets when it comes to data and engagement, but broadly, they are best equipped to mobilize around collective priorities.

For each opportunity, we'll include a reference for the other sectors to which this opportunity could apply:

COMMUNITIES & COMMUNITY-BASED ORGANIZATIONS

1. SUPPORT GOVERNMENT LEARNING IN TRAINING, VALUE ASSESSMENT, AND LEARNING FROM COMMUNITIES

THE *INSIGHT*

Communities intimately know the environmental and climate issues with which they grapple, and often understand potential solutions. But avenues for communicating information and solutions to local governments often remain unclear or are inaccessible. There are gaps between knowledge held by communities and what local decision makers understand as data, as well as how political processes dictate how such information will be used. Such information asymmetries are exacerbated because, as Alicia Scott, the Just Energy Manager at [Partnership for Southern Equity](#), noted,

“the public often thinks that leaders will absorb community issues, and then, stop talking to their lawmakers. There’s a need for regular check-ins since lawmakers might not know a problem exists at all.”

This points to the need for local governments to make it easy for communities to be in conversation, to understand how input is incorporated, and how accountability will be tracked and communicated back to communities.

THE *OPPORTUNITY*

Facilitating government learning from communities will look different in different contexts, but can be a first step for community-developed solutions to enter policy conversations and ultimately, improve the terms through which individuals and groups take part in society. There is an opportunity to change the conventional paradigm, which dictates that communities should be trained to fit into government-designed processes. Instead, it is possible to implement models where government does the facilitative and iterative work of creating value-imbued engagement that prioritizes trust, accountability, and transparency, supported by community input and data.

There is an opportunity for local, state, and tribal governments to interrogate how these values are understood by both government employees and communities, and how they are incorporated into planning processes. Sarah Yeager, Climate and Energy Planner with the City of Pittsburgh, pointed to the need to deliberately address trust:

“I think we’ve seen a lot of trust breakdown with some of our community organizations or community members, because we do the engagement during the planning process, but then either implementation falls off, or there’s not that kind of continued engagement through the full project. We have had to freeze our whole [neighborhood planning] process to have a meeting just to talk about that trust issue. If there were new employees on the city side, or new staff coming to it, we could make sure that we were very clear on what the trust issues were and what the history in that community was [...] Having that kind of ability to change our process, change our timelines, to really take the time to listen.”

Continued on next page

COMMUNITIES & COMMUNITY-BASED ORGANIZATIONS

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Government learning from communities is inherently linked to capacity-building, as well. Jessi Eidbo, Senior Climate Change Data Analyst at Hennepin County, noted:

“Primary capacity limiters feel two-fold—not knowing what we don’t know and navigating the behemoth of the county. To build capacity, we’ve been working a lot on networking, relationship building, consensus building, and partnerships. I think these builders work both internally and externally with community partners and stakeholders.”

Additionally, there is an opportunity for intermediary organizations (community-based, capacity building, or research-focused) to support these processes, with advocacy and data literacy training programs for communities and government employees alike. Training that is issue-based and place-tailored will lower barriers to interaction. A major theme in the Brain Trust was the insight that communities require specific pieces of information that would be useful in making an effective pitch to a policymaker. Data literacy is an important aspect of communities being able to uncover useful data, and of government agencies being able to integrate evidence into policy making. Uncovering that data and integrating evidence also relies on the openness of the data in question. This points to the need for continued maintenance of open government data initiatives (and user interaction within those initiatives) alongside any data literacy training.⁵

⁵ [Maintaining user interaction and engagement to realize reusability is explored in “Beyond the supply side: Use and impact of municipal open data in the US” \(Wilson and Cong 2021\) with examples in Louisville, Buffalo, and Philadelphia.](#)

INSIGHTS & OPPORTUNITIES

CIVIL SOCIETY
ORGANIZATIONS &
ACADEMICS

Civil society organizations and academics working in local climate and environmental planning spaces actively create infrastructure to support open data, knowledge sharing, and governance feedback loops.

For each opportunity, we'll include a reference for the other sectors to which this opportunity could apply:

CIVIL SOCIETY ORGANIZATIONS & ACADEMICS

1. IDENTIFY SPACES FOR DATA COLLABORATIVES IN TANDEM WITH COMMUNITIES AND LOCAL GOVERNMENT

THE **INSIGHT**

Data collaboratives present a particularly promising opportunity for civil society to conscientiously build and maintain environment and climate spaces for data that intersect many issues and are shared by different contributors. More and more localities are imagining spaces where governments and communities can share and manage data collaboratively.

THE **OPPORTUNITY**

Data collaboratives are becoming more common and larger in scale, so it is necessary to create these spaces with three specific considerations: 1) data type, 2) metadata curation and 3) training. First, it is important to recognize the need for the input and management of different kinds of data, including qualitative data. Data collaboratives often focus on quantitative data, which can undermine the validity of many community engagement processes where written and spoken input is offered. Data collaboratives can offer a historical catalog of community engagement with utility for communities and government alike. In practice, this collaborative structure could be used in government-led pre-planning assessments to reduce community asks for data they've already collected and provided.

Second, it is necessary to build in intentional space to foster shared metadata curation practices with the communities and governments served. Such a process can intrinsically support prioritizing and bridging gaps in knowledge. This is also a way to develop value from the beginning and from the bottom-up, derived from the needs of the community. This approach can be integrated into other engagement processes and [can be pivotal to the success of a data collaborative](#).

Finally, civil society organizations and academics must build in intentional training space for local government employees and communities. Civic tech tools can only go as far as staff and employees know how to use them. A working knowledge of data management, ["good enough" data](#), and community engagement with data should be key elements of such a space designed for governments building and maintaining data collaboratives.

DATA COLLABORATIVES

There are quite a few ways to think about data collaboratives, but the term encompasses "a form of a partnership in which a variety of parties, such as government, operators, companies and others, collaborate to exchange and integrate data in order to help solve public problems or create public value."⁶ This theoretical underpinning points to data-related innovations that create public value through the exchange of data, allowing, broadly, for situational awareness and response, public service design and delivery, knowledge creation and transfer, prediction and forecasting, and impact assessment and evaluation.⁷ While there are different types of data collaboratives that have restricted access or independent uses, this brief largely focuses on collaboratives that are open access, have cooperative uses, and are focused on open governance practices, and community data. A cooperatively used data collaborative means that data suppliers and users can decide the focus of the data use and analysis in partnership.⁸ Examples can be found using GovLab's Data Collaboratives Explorer.

⁶ Susha, I., Janssen, M., Verhulst, S. (2017). *Data Collaboratives as a New Frontier of Cross-Sector Partnerships in the Age of Open Data: Taxonomy Development*. Proceedings of the 50th Hawaii International Conference on System Sciences, 2691-2700. <https://scholarspace.manoa.hawaii.edu/bitstream/10125/41481/1/paper0332.pdf>

⁷ Verhulst, S., Young, A., Srinivasan, P. *Introduction to Data Collaboratives*. GovLab. <https://datacollaboratives.org/static/files/data-collaboratives-intro.pdf>

⁸ More on [the variables of engagement and accessibility of data collaboratives from GovLab](#).

INSIGHTS & OPPORTUNITIES

PHILANTHROPY

Public and private philanthropy can be part of a broader cultural shift to prioritize collaboration in local environmental and climate planning. There are opportunities for funders to offer capital and build technical capacity with organizations that pilot solutions and smooth collaborative engagement.

For each opportunity, we'll include a reference for the other sectors to which this opportunity could apply:

PHILANTHROPY

1. PROVIDE UNRESTRICTED FUNDING AND GENERAL OPERATING SUPPORT

THE **INSIGHT**

It has long been stated that community-based organizations need unrestricted general operating support so that programming can [run smoothly and get the highest return on impact](#). Emi Wang emphasized:

"If you're investing in a group, you are trusting them, and what groups need is unrestricted general operating funds. Instead of chasing these big ideas, just trust in the groups and the infrastructure."

A focus on general operating support paves the way for a broader cultural shift within philanthropy that prioritizes trust, relationships, and addressing fundamental power asymmetries. It also opens the door to continued innovation, as it enables organizations to shift course when needed, and to consider new, pressing, or relevant data points and information.

THE **OPPORTUNITY**

There is an opportunity for philanthropic organizations to prioritize collaborative values in their grantmaking and actively encourage and provide unrestricted general operating support. Providing such support allows organizations to respond to new data or unforeseen or critical situations in a way that isn't driven solely by project deliverables, but by intended impact in the form of missions, visions and theories of change. This ultimately enables increased learning as organizations can uncover new needs and prototype original solutions. In the spirit of open, this increased and dynamic learning can also provide an opportunity for lessons to be shared among philanthropy and other mission-aligned organizations so that environment and climate work can be

PHILANTHROPY

2. SUPPORT WIDESPREAD LEARNING AND ADAPTATION OF RESOURCES BY AMPLIFYING GRANTEES' WORK AND SUPPORTING NETWORK-BUILDING ACTIVITIES

THE **INSIGHT**

Philanthropies sit at the intersection of many interests, expertise, communities, and organizations. The birds-eye view this position affords them allows for efficient resource provision. Participants in the Brain Trust pointed to the need for access to consolidated models and case studies of collaborative governance between government and community, including data that is open, publicly available, and downloadable. Many organizations are doing the work of creating and curating resources and thought leadership based on their experiences in environmental and climate planning, and there is an opportunity for philanthropy to support network building so that these learnings can be shared and accessed more broadly.

THE **OPPORTUNITY**

Philanthropic organizations can leverage their assets to not only build connections between their grantees, but also fund resulting coalitions and collaborations. Philanthropic entities can also fund organizations that are working as intermediaries and network-builders, as they often have a farther reach and more intimate knowledge of network needs.

Networks between funded communities can reduce duplication, promote open data practices, and bring organizations together to share successful models and best practices. An example of an organization doing this work is the [Tribal Exchange Network Group](#), which helps to support tribes' management, analysis, and sharing of their environmental data.

Within these networks, funding support from philanthropy can contribute to modular and adaptable resources that are accessible, shareable, and reusable. Data sharing agreements, policy and advocacy templates related to environmental data, and best practices for data governance can provide technical guidance that can be adapted for context. Beyond funding the creation and management of these technical resources, funders can support organizations to create and maintain online spaces to house materials and host in-person and virtual knowledge exchanges on engagement and data models.

CONCLUSION

Communities, organizations, and local, tribal, and state governments have the potential to advance innovative and inclusive environmental planning, as they are more intimately connected to community priorities than the federal government. Great strides have been made in environmental and climate spaces at these levels through multi-sectoral processes, but there is more to do. A smoother, more equitable planning process is possible through:

- value-driven data engagement and sharing that respects community knowledge and enables government to learn from them;
- capacity building opportunities for both communities and government;
- legal, human, and digital infrastructure to enable data sharing and access;
- collaborative resource creation and sharing to support learning; and
- agile and trusting funding structures.

This brief points to ways to address these needs, offering opportunities that can be integrated across government, civil society, and philanthropy. As climate change and pollution emergencies create more complex and immediate community needs, deliberately designing data driven planning processes can create a foundation for communities, now and in the future.

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BRAIN TRUST PARTICIPANTS

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